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Enhancing Christian Education Ministry of a Church Through Social Media Platforms

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Abstract

Christian Education is essential for church growth and individual maturity in faith. Social media platforms provide this means. Christian education is the process of teaching and learning based on Christian doctrines, principles, beliefs, and values with the aim of developing spiritual, intellectual and moral growth of people. While social media platforms are online spaces where users create, share and interact with content, information, or other users in a virtual environment. This study investigates the relationship between social media and Christian education ministry. The objective of the study is to examine the influence of various social media platforms on Christian education ministries of the church. Descriptive survey research design was employed, surveying 274 church members and conducting interviews with 10 church leaders. Finding revealed significant correlations between social media usage and increased engagement in Christian education ($r = 0.35$, $p < 0.01$). Finding further revealed a significant improvement in Christian education ministry in the church employing social media platforms commonly used by her members. Also, using social media platforms have enabled more people to be educated and creating a faith-based relationship among people of different backgrounds. Social media is also useful to growing body of research on social media impact on Christian education ministries. In conclusion, social media platforms have greatly boosted the work of Christian education ministry of the church to reaching wider audience in the shortest time with limited resources and risks. Therefore, this study recommends that there should be improvement of internet awareness, increase social media usage and encouragement of massive participation of Christians for effective delivery and dissemination of Christian education ministry of the local churches.

Keywords: Christian Education Ministry of a Church, Church Growth, Social Media Platforms

Introduction

Christian Education in a local church has been a thing of physical contact and present. You have to come to the church premises to be taught. Church leaders fix a time within the week where everyone meets under the same roof, either in groups or the whole congregation, and enjoy the teaching-learning process. This method enhances social bonds and provides adequate feedback during meetings. However, with the advent of social media, things have changed drastically. Social media has transformed how people interact, learn, and share information. Over the years, social media has made communication and relationships easy and quick to access (Afolaranmi, 2019). The global village phenomenon has allowed people of diverse cultural backgrounds to meet anywhere and anytime, irrespective of space and distance. One can be in London and meet people in Lagos in real time. This is indeed remarkable. Social media has eliminated all barriers of distance, time, and venue. This development has made Christian Education accessible with ease in a local church setting. The goal of Christian Education is that people at all levels and ages receive sound teaching and live out what they are being taught.

Meanwhile, the Christian Education Division of a local church is an arm of the church responsible for the sharing, delivering, and disseminating Christian teaching, beliefs, values, doctrines, instruction, warning,

and norms that ensure spiritual maturity and conformity to Christ-likeness. The teachings distinguish Christianity from other religions. Christian educators must be adequately tutored in Christian faith and beliefs. They must put everything in place to ascertain no heresy or deviation. Church leaders must put round pegs in round holes by ensuring the right people handle this kind of teaching. We cannot overemphasize the need for Christian education in a local church. It is vital to local Church ministries.

Literature Review

Christian Education

These are some definitions of Christian Education. Habermas (2008) defines Christian Education as "the process of sharing content with persons in the context of their community and society. The word "content" as used in the definition refers to the Bible and other traditions of faith that are shared among followers of Christ. It is a process by which those who have experienced a personal spiritual rebirth in their relationship with God partner with the indwelling Holy Spirit to grow the image of Christ (Lester, 2001). This definition points out a few things: Christian teaching is meant for the regenerated, and the Holy Spirit helps us grow into Christ's image through the education provided.

Christian education is a divine effort as well as a human effort. The efforts or activities are geared toward disseminating biblical knowledge and translating it into values and attitudes of becoming like Christ through the power of the Holy Spirit. Every believer must acquire sufficient knowledge of Christ for their growth in faith. The church must do all it can to promote sound Christian teaching in the church.

A local church is a body of believers formally organised on gospel principles, meeting regularly for evangelism, nurture, fellowship, and worship. A local church refers to both the physical structure and the worshippers. This is where worship takes place and where people congregate and fellowship together.

Likewise, social media refers to online platforms or tools that allow users to create, share, or exchange information, ideas, pictures/videos, and other content in virtual communities and networks. Also, "Social media are online platforms that allow users to create and share content, participate in online discussions, and connect with others in virtual communities." (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010, p. 61). Examples of social media are Facebook, Instagram, Telegram, Tiktok, Threads, Twitter, Snapchat and so on.

Characteristics of Social Media

1. **Interactivity:** Users can interact with each other and with content (O'Reilly, 2005). Social media helps Christian educators connect with their members by providing the right content using virtual space and networks. It also ensures smooth relationships among members.
2. **User-generated content:** Users create and share content (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010). Through Social Media platforms, Christian Educators develop curricula and turn the curriculum into suitable content for respective users.
3. **Virtual communities:** Users connect and interact in online spaces (Rheingold, 1993). There is a community of Christian brothers and sisters who share the same values and ideas and collaborate into a loving family in a virtual space.
4. **Social networking:** Users build relationships and networks (Boyd & Ellison, 2007). Social media creates an interconnectivity and interpersonal relationship among Christian educators and their members, eliminating distance and time barriers.

Types of Social Media

1. **Social networking sites** (e.g., Facebook, Twitter, WhatsApp, etc.) have interface connections through text, audio and video means. They are more accessible and broadly used by Social media audiences than any other interacting sites.

2. **Blogs and microblogging platforms** (e.g., WordPress, Twitter, Tumblr): These platforms make communicating with the audience quickly easier.
3. **Content-sharing sites** (e.g., YouTube, Instagram, TikTok, Pinterest, LinkedIn): In these sites, one can text update, comment, share images or videos and any file format containing data.
4. **Forums and discussion boards** (e.g., Reddit, Quora): An Internet forum or messages board is an online discussion site where people can hold conversations in the form of posted messages. Meanwhile, the Discussion Board is a social media platform where users can engage in focused conversations and share information on various topics of interest (Krishnan & Rogers, 2015).

Social media's influence on Christian education is multifaceted:

1. **Information dissemination:** Social media platforms facilitate sharing of biblical teachings and resources (Kang, 2015). Christian Educators find it easier to communicate their minds to their target audience and use social media platforms. Sunday School preparatory classes can now engage thousands of people through Telegram, WhatsApp, etc.
2. **Community engagement:** Social media fosters online communities, enhancing discipleship and fellowship (Campbell, 2012). Christian families have been emerging on social media circles. Special media makes people to know themselves better,
3. **Digital evangelism:** Social media provides opportunities for evangelism and outreach (Hutchison, 2017). These online platforms have become a means of sharing information and even avenues for holding Church worship services (Afolaranmi, 2019). Social media has allowed Christian educators to reach people and tribes that are strictly Christian messages and followers. Also, a wider audience can be reached using various social media platforms, e.g., WhatsApp, Instagram, and Facebook, unlike physical meetings.

Methodology

This study adopted Descriptive Survey Research Design. Two hundred and seventy-four (274) church members completed an online survey assessing social media usage and Christian education engagement. They have responded to the correlation between social media and Christian Education quickly within few days, which is also evidence of the effectiveness of social media in reaching people nowadays. 10 church leaders participated in semi-structured interviews exploring social media's impact on Christian education.

Data Analysis and Discussion

Descriptive statistics and thematic analysis revealed:

1. Increased engagement: Social media usage correlated with increased participation in Christian education ($r = 0.35, p < 0.01$).
2. Information overload: Church leaders expressed concerns about information overload and decreased attention span.

Table 1: Distribution of Availability of Christian Education Ministries in the Church

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Yes	269	99.26	99.26	99.26
No	1	0.37	0.37	99.66
Not Yet	0	0	0	
No answer	0	0	0	
Total	270	99.66	99.66	

Source: Authors' Construct, 2024

Table 1 presents the distribution of the respondents by their participation in Christian education in their churches through Sunday School, Discipleship programme, Children and Teenagers ministry, etc. This means that 269 participants out of 270 who responded to the question observed Sunday School, Discipleship Training Ministry, and Children and Teenagers Ministries in their churches. This is almost 100%, which is a remarkable feat that the Churches are involved in educating their members on the teaching and values of Christianity.

Table 2: Distribution of Social Media Usage in the Church

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Yes	252	92.99	92.99	99.26
No	10	3.69	3.69	99.66
Not Yet	8	2.95	2.95	
No Answer	1	0.37	0.37	
Total	270	99.17	99.66	

Source: Authors' Construct, 2024

The table above indicated that about 92.99% use social media to propagate sound biblical and Christian teachings, 3.69% don't use it at all, and the remaining 3.54% work independently. This is encouraging and can still increase if all hands are on the desk.

Table 3: Distribution of Different Social Media Platforms Usage in the Church

Social Media Platforms	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Social Networking Sites e.g. Facebook, WhatsApp, Twitter etc.	259	82.48	82.48	82.49
Content Sharing Sites e.g. YouTube, Instagram etc.	44	14.01	14.01	96.49
Forum and Discussion Boards e.g. Reddit, Quora et	11	3.5	3.5	99.99
Total	314	99.99	99.99	

Source: Authors' Construct, 2024

The results indicated that social networking sites such as WhatsApp and Facebook are employed more by the church to reach her audience with 82.48%, unlike Content Sharing Sites (e.g., YouTube and Instagram) which has 14.01% and Forum and Discussion Boards has only 3.5% (e.g., Reddit. Quora) types of social media. This implies that many people use Facebook and WhatsApp to interact with one another in the Church. So, churches should make her presence known and felt using Social Networking sites to reach her audiences the more.

Table 4: Distribution of Enhancement of Christian Education Content through Social Media Platforms

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Agreed	187	69	69	69
Partially Agreed	75	27.68	27.68	96.69
Disagree	9	3.32	3.32	100
Total Disagreed	0	0	0	
Total	271	100	100	

Source: Authors' Construct, 2024

The above result showed that 69 percent admit firmly that social media has enhanced the dissemination of Christian education content in their churches, 27.68 percent partially agreed and 3.32 percent disagreed. This study shows that social media can help the church to transmit her messages, information, ideas, etc to her members and outside world.

Table 5: Distribution of Effect Social Media Platforms in Reaching Wider Audience

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Agreed	214	78.68	78.68	78.68
Partially Agreed	54	19.85	19.85	98.53
Disagree	4	1.47	1.47	100
Total Disagreed	0	0	0	
Total	272	100	100	

Source: Authors' Construct, 2024

The table above revealed that 78.68.04% strongly agreed and 19.85% partially agreed that social media can help the church reach an audience more than meeting physically. Just 1.47 percent disagreed, just four persons out of 272 that participated in the research. By implication, churches should encourage both physical and online meetings. People who can come to the church should come, while those who cannot come for one reason or another should join online. Therefore, today's churches should use virtual space to meet the spiritual needs of those online.

Table 6: Distribution of Positive and Negative Effect Social Media Platforms in Promoting Christian Education in the Local Church

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Agreed	22	8.06	8.06	8.06
Partially Agreed	67	24.54	24.54	32.06
Disagree	148	54.21	54.21	86.81
Total Disagreed	36	13.19	13.19	100
Total	273	100	100	

Source: Authors' Construct, 2024

Table 6 deals with the effect of social media platforms in promoting Christian education ministries in the church. It shows that 8.06% strongly agreed and 24.54% partially agreed that social media creates more harm than good in promoting Christian education in the local church. On the other hand, 67.4% disagreed with

the above assertion. Thus, social media has some adverse effects, such as distractions, exposure to explicit content, hacking, cyberbullying, and so on, but the advantages outweigh the disadvantages if it is well used.

Table 7: Distribution of Control and Guide for Social Media Users in Sharing Christian Education Contents

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Agreed	213	78.6	78.6	78.6
Partially Agreed	44	16.24	16.24	94.84
Disagree	10	3.69	3.69	98.53
Total Disagreed	4	1.48	1.48	100
Total	271	100	100	

Source: Authors' Construct, 2024

The table above shows that 78.6 strongly agreed and 16.24 partially agreed that there is a need for firm control of various social media platforms and guidelines on the mode of operation for both the members of the platforms and the church leadership in these platforms. However, less than 5% disagreed with the need for strict control and rules to guide the operation. This shows that social media handlers should have a clear cut of the modulus operandi for all on their platforms. Everyone participating in this space must be ready to abide by the rules regulating the operation.

Table 8: Distribution of Effect of Social Media on Physical Meetings and Members' Closeness in a Local Church

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Agreed	74	27.01	27.01	27.01
Partially Agreed	109	39.78	39.78	66.79
Disagree	81	29.56	29.56	96.35
Total Disagreed	10	3.65	3.65	100
Total	274	100	100	

Source: Authors' Construct, 2024

More than 60 percent think social media endangers physical meetings and reduces closeness among local church members. As good as social media is, if care is not taken, it can cause great havoc to community living and fellowship of brethren. This is corroborated in Hebrews 10: 25, "Let us not give up meeting together, as some are in the habit of doing, but let us encourage one another — and all the more as you see the Day approaching. NIV" Meeting together as brothers and sisters in the Lord is greatly encouraged in the Bible, and we cannot underemphasize it because of social media.

Table 9: Distribution of Whether Social Media Create Distraction While Sharing Christian Education Content

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Agreed	30	11.03	11.03	11.03
Partially Agreed	84	30.88	30.88	41.91
Disagree	133	48.9	48.9	90.81
Total Disagreed	25	9.19	9.19	100

Total	274	100	100
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Source: Authors' Construct, 2024

Table 9 deals with whether or not social media distracts in sharing Christian Education content. The study revealed that 58.09 percent disagreed that social media would be distracting when sharing Christian education content. While 41.91 percent posited that there would be a distraction when using social media to share Christian content. This concerns how individuals can control social media usage when sharing Christian Education content.

Open Question: Participants responded to using social media platforms to share and create content for the Christian education division of the church. The majority welcome the use of social media platforms and encourage churches that have not been using them to start in earnest. They mentioned some of the advantages inherent in using social media platforms to share Christian education content, which among the others:

1. Social media helps to reach members across the globe, bringing God's word to their doorstep.
2. Social media is a promising avenue for determining information among members of the Christian education division.
3. Social media enhances the growth of Christian education ministries and, in the long run, church expansion.
4. Social media platforms provide easy ways to get through to many audiences, impacting the church's large population at a time.
5. Since the world is going digital, it will be good for Christian educators to employ social media platforms to reach and stay connected to prospective and potential members.
6. Social media can also project positively the image of the Christian education division of the church to the outside world.
7. Some participants believe it is part of an end-time strategy to make the gospel reach everyone before the end of time, as Jesus mentioned to the disciples in Matthew 24.
8. Employing Social media platforms to reach church members is cost-effective these days due to the barrier of distance, high cost of transportation, busy schedules in offices, working night, traffic congestion, making people be on the road for hours, etc. Social media platforms now provide the much-needed solution to these challenges.
9. It saves cost to the church; instead of spending thousands of naira on getting hard-copy materials, soft-copy versions can easily get and used.
10. Social media platforms are youth-friendly and can be used to reach and sustain them in the church.

However, some notable disadvantages of using social media were also pointed out in the online questionnaire and interview:

1. Social media platforms can create distractions for some users.
2. Some Social media sites post the risk of leading users to destructive and dangerous scenes and information that can lead to harmful activities.
3. If not properly monitored and controlled, it can be misused and abused, defeating the essence of creating it in the first place.
4. It can endanger church community living and closeness among members.
5. The older generation sometimes finds it hard to use social media. So, if care is not taken, some elderly ones can be neglected if the church is greatly dependent on social media to reach the members of the Christian education division of the church.

Conclusion

Christian education is germane to the growth and maturity of the believers in the church. So, the church must allow all the aspects of Christian education to be fully developed and integrated into the lives of its members. Sunday School ministry, Discipleship Training ministry, Children and teenagers' ministries etc should be prioritized in every local church. One of the sure ways to engage members of the church is the use of social media platforms for sharing information and transmitting godly content that will benefit the members. So, social media is very important in the life of the Christian education division of a church. Social media is the new way to go and should be included in the church community's life, especially in the area of sharing Christian education content. Social media has helped to reach a global community of believers and broken the barriers of distance. It's a way of getting through to many audiences, thereby impacting a large population at a time.

Churches should intentionally integrate social media into their educational strategies. By teaching and encouraging members to use social media, we can take Christian education to another level. The knowledge of the Word of God will surely increase. Thus, social media is the tool that God has given humankind to make the easy spread of the Word of God possible. Social media should be seen as an end-time strategy to make the gospel reach everyone before the end of time. This was confirmed in Matthew 24: 14, "This good news of the kingdom will be proclaimed in all the world as a testimony to all nations. And the end will come. One of the prerequisites for the world to an end is that everyone must hear the gospel of the Lord Jesus Christ. Therefore, through various social media platforms with aggressive evangelism, one can listen to the good news that Jesus saves.

Recommendations

1. Social media is a good initiative and must be sustained. It is a great innovation, and it has come to stay. Social media is making life easier and improving ministry.
2. The church should employ social media but should not be a replacement for physical meetings that will lead to the idea of Christian community life and fellowship. Church leaders should still encourage members to participate in church activities and programmes on a physical basis. This makes Hebrews 10:25 "Let us not give up meeting together, as some are in the habit of doing, but let us encourage one another – and all the more as you see the Day approaching" a reality.
3. The Church should make her presence known and felt using Social Networking sites such as WhatsApp, Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, YouTube, etc. We can spread the church tentacle to those outside the church using various social media platforms.
4. The Church should reach its audiences more using various social media platforms. It should be used to disseminate Christian Education content with the purpose of reaching a larger and wider audience.
5. Churches should encourage both physical and online meetings. Those members who cannot be present in the church should be reached through various social media platforms so as not to be left out.
6. There should be strict control and rules to guide social media users in sharing and benefiting from Christian Education content. Church Social media handlers should clearly state what rules are to be followed when in the platforms. People should be encouraged to use social media for godly and edifying purposes, not for personal gratification. Generally, the youth are always on one social media platform or another; hence, Christian educators and church leaders should encourage them to use platforms for godly and positive purposes that will expand the kingdom of God.
7. Social media is full of good and negative information. Thus, it can promote positive and negative attitudes and values. It is, therefore, expedient to teach youths in the Church to use social media platforms for positive and godly impacts among their peers and in the global space. Also, they

discourage the youths from involving in social media vices like pornography, cyberbullying, cybercrime, and other distractions.

8. Social media is viable for church fellowship and expansion through Christian Education. Social media should even create more bonds among members. However, Christian meetings and fellowship should also be encouraged.
9. Social media is full of sound and negative information. Thus, it can promote positive and negative attitudes and values. It is, therefore, expedient to teach youths in the Church to use social media platforms for positive and godly impacts among their peers and in the global space. Also, they discourage the youths from involving in social media vices like pornography, cyberbullying, cybercrime, and other distractions.

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